

FLEXURAL-TWIST COUPLING OF ANISOTROPIC BEAMS

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SUMMARY

Flexural-twist coupling is significant in many aerospace structures. This paper investigates the flexural-twist coupling of CFRP beams of varying lay-up from experimental, simple analytical, and finite element approaches.

Although the computational capability now exists to undertake dynamic analyses of large composite structures using detailed 3-dimensional finite element models, such analyses are still too time consuming for use in design optimisation.

The behaviour of slender structures (such as wind turbine or helicopter rotor blades) is therefore often idealised by 1-dimensional beams with associated cross sectional stiffness (and mass) properties, in which the beam strains are related to the applied forces via a 6x6 cross sectional stiffness matrix.

Flexural-twist coupling is specified by the K_{45} term from the cross sectional stiffness matrix. This paper clarifies the physical interpretation of K_{45} ; describes an experimental technique used to derive the flap torsion coupling of composite beams, and compares experimental results with analytical and finite element predictions.

Keywords: Composite, Coupling, Stiffness matrix

1. INTRODUCTION

Slender structures are often idealised as 1-dimensional beams, with associated cross sectional stiffness (and mass) properties. The elastic coupling terms of anisotropic composite materials can give rise to non-intuitive couplings in the behaviour of structures made from them. The coupling between bending and torsion is of particular interest in the aeroelastic tailoring of aerodynamic structures such as helicopter rotor blades.

Consider the beam in the global co-ordinate system shown in Figure 1. Flap bending is defined as bending about the Y-axis, which gives a tip deflection in the Z-direction. Similarly, lag bending is defined as bending about the Z-axis. This paper compares the

results of experimental, numerical, and simple analytical methods of determining K_{45} for a number of CFRP beams of solid rectangular cross-section.

Figure 1 Beam global co-ordinate system

Referring again to Figure 1, it is seen that the beam strains are related to the applied forces via the 6x6 cross sectional stiffness matrix

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_{xy} \\ N_{xz} \\ M_{yz} \\ M_y \\ M_z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{13} & K_{14} & K_{15} & K_{16} \\ K_{12} & K_{22} & K_{23} & K_{24} & K_{25} & K_{26} \\ K_{13} & K_{23} & K_{33} & K_{34} & K_{35} & K_{36} \\ K_{14} & K_{24} & K_{34} & K_{44} & K_{45} & K_{46} \\ K_{15} & K_{25} & K_{35} & K_{45} & K_{55} & K_{56} \\ K_{16} & K_{26} & K_{36} & K_{46} & K_{56} & K_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \kappa_{yz} \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

or via the compliance matrix (which is the inverse of the stiffness matrix)

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \kappa_{yz} \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & S_{14} & S_{15} & S_{16} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} & S_{24} & S_{25} & S_{26} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} & S_{34} & S_{35} & S_{36} \\ S_{14} & S_{24} & S_{34} & S_{44} & S_{45} & S_{46} \\ S_{15} & S_{25} & S_{35} & S_{45} & S_{55} & S_{56} \\ S_{16} & S_{26} & S_{36} & S_{46} & S_{56} & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_{xy} \\ N_{xz} \\ M_{yz} \\ M_y \\ M_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

However, it is much easier to experimentally derive compliance terms than stiffness terms, and hence the value of K_{45} is calculated from the inverse of the compliance matrix. The K_{45} stiffness term can usually be (partially) decoupled from the full 6x6 stiffness matrix. This is the case for the laminated CFRP beams that will be examined in this project. It is therefore not necessary to derive the entire compliance matrix in order to determine K_{45} .

2. TEST SPECIMENS

Eight 1 metre long CFRP beams of rectangular cross section (approximately 40mm x 8mm) were provided by Agusta-Westland Helicopters for experimental testing. These beams were originally the subject of testing undertaken by Diamond [1]. Each beam was

manufactured with a unique lay-up. The lay-up and exact geometry of each beam is therefore summarised by Table 1.

Table 1 Geometry and lay-ups of available test specimens

Beam	Lay-up	Mean width (mm)	Mean depth (mm)
1	$[0]_{60}$	40.18	7.93
2	$[+45]_{60}$	40.41	7.97
3	$[+45]_{30}[-45]_{30}$	40.29	7.92
4	$[+/-45]_{30}[-/+45]_{30}$	40.28	7.96
5	$[+15]_{60}$	40.19	7.96
6	$[+15]_{30}[-15]_{30}$	40.71	8.00
7	$[+30]_{60}$	40.15	7.99
8	$[+30]_{30}[-30]_{30}$	40.13	7.99

Each beam is constructed from 60 plies of unidirectional carbon, laid up in the global xy -plane as shown on Figure 2. Although 60 plies of 0.125mm thick UD carbon would normally give a total thickness of 7.5mm, the beams are all approximately 8mm thick with the additional thickness comprising excess resin. The material properties quoted by the supplier are therefore not valid for this volume fraction.

Figure 2 Orientation of layers in DERA-manufactured beams

Diamond [1] addressed this problem by measuring the overall bending and twisting flexibilities of Beam 1 (manufactured from 0° plies) and back calculating the material properties. These values of material properties (given in Table 2) were then applied to the calculations for the remaining beams. In the current paper, the material stiffness has been recalculated at a lamina level for the lower volume fraction. Both approaches assume that the excess resin is uniformly distributed throughout the thickness of the laminate, although the validity of this assumption was not investigated.

Table 2 CFRP material properties calculated by Diamond [1]

Properties	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
Carbon XAS 913c	124.0	9.4	9.4	4.6	4.6	2.4	0.26	0.26	0.30

3. ANALOGY WITH CLASSICAL LAMINATE THEORY

Due to their construction (each beam can be considered as a thick laminate of finite width), there is replication of some of the terms in the ABD laminate stiffness matrix and the 1-dimensional beam stiffness matrix. Equivalent terms are shown by identically coloured boxes in the matrices of Figure 3.

$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{13} & K_{14} & K_{15} & K_{16} \\ K_{12} & K_{22} & K_{23} & K_{24} & K_{25} & K_{26} \\ K_{13} & K_{23} & K_{33} & K_{34} & K_{35} & K_{36} \\ K_{14} & K_{24} & K_{34} & K_{44} & K_{45} & K_{46} \\ K_{15} & K_{25} & K_{35} & K_{45} & K_{55} & K_{56} \\ K_{16} & K_{26} & K_{36} & K_{46} & K_{56} & K_{66} \end{bmatrix}$
Laminate stiffness matrix	1-D beam stiffness matrix

Figure 3 Equivalence of terms in ABD laminate matrix and 1-D beam stiffness matrix

The underlying assumptions of classical laminate theory are not met - in particular, for the samples studied in this research (where the laminate thickness is approximately 20% of the laminate width) shear stresses in the laminate are not uniform across the width, but may be envisaged as a flow within the cross section in closed contours. Although this will lead to inaccurate stiffness values predicted by this method, the other insights provided by this theory justify its use here. In particular, classical laminate theory allows the locations of zero and non-zero terms in the 6x6 beam cross sectional stiffness matrix to be predicted. Since all plies lie parallel to the x - y plane, the third and sixth rows and columns can be decoupled from the rest of the matrix. The location of non-zero terms in the 6x6 cross-sectional stiffness matrix depend on the lay-up (Symmetric balanced, Symmetric unbalanced, and Anti-symmetric), as shown below.

For Symmetric, balanced lay-ups (i.e. Beams 1, 4) the beam cross sectional stiffness matrix is populated as shown opposite. The 2 x 2 sub-matrix containing the S_{44} , S_{45} and S_{55} terms can be decoupled from the full 6x6 compliance matrix.

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & S_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{44} & S_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{45} & S_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

For Symmetric, unbalanced lay-ups (i.e. Beams 2, 5, 7) the beam cross sectional stiffness matrix is populated as shown opposite. The 2 x 2 sub-matrix containing the S_{44} , S_{45} and S_{55} terms can be decoupled from the full 6x6 compliance matrix.

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{44} & S_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{45} & S_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

For anti-symmetric lay-ups (i.e. Beams, 3, 6, 8), the beam cross sectional stiffness matrix is populated as shown opposite. K_{45} is predicted to be zero.

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & 0 & 0 & S_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & S_{22} & 0 & 0 & S_{25} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ S_{14} & 0 & 0 & S_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & S_{25} & 0 & 0 & S_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

4. PHYSICAL INTERPRETATION OF K_{45}

Two possible physical interpretations can be applied to K_{45} :

1. The torque (M_{yz}) when one unit of flapwise bending curvature (κ_y) is applied (and all other strains are constrained to zero)

$$M_{yz} = K_{14}\epsilon_x + K_{24}\gamma_{xy} + K_{34}\gamma_{xz} + K_{44}\kappa_{yz} + K_{45}\kappa_y + K_{46}\kappa_z \quad (3)$$

Thus, if a constant flapwise bending curvature is applied to the beam, the value of K_{45} can be calculated directly from the torque required to give no end rotation.

2. The moment (M_y) when one unit of twist (κ_{xy}) is applied (and all other strains are constrained to zero).

$$M_y = K_{15}\epsilon_x + K_{25}\gamma_{xy} + K_{35}\gamma_{xz} + K_{45}\kappa_{yz} + K_{55}\kappa_y + K_{56}\kappa_z \quad (4)$$

Thus if a constant twist rate is applied to the beam, the value of K_{45} can be calculated directly from the bending moment required to give no curvature.

It is worth noting that K_{44} is not the “torsional stiffness” – torsional stiffness is given by $1/S_{44}$. Similarly, K_{55} is not the “bending stiffness” – bending stiffness is given by $1/S_{55}$

5. FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

A finite element model was constructed for each of the 8 beams. These were subjected to bending and torsion displacements with appropriate end constraints. This is similar to the approach adopted by Hill and Weaver [3] who apply four different beam end displacements (along with appropriate support conditions), to derive the entire 6x6 stiffness matrix for any arbitrary beam section.

Note that the finite element models all used a nominal 40mm x 8mm cross-section and material properties equal to the “corrected” values calculate by Diamond [1] in Table 2.

6. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Since the reduction of the 3-dimensional behaviour to an idealised 1-dimensional beam inherently assumes a linear system, it is possible to calculate the stiffness matrix terms from the results of a cantilever bend test. The torsion force required to prevent twisting

is relatively easy to determine in this type of test. A schematic diagram of the experimental set-up (complete with charts of bending moment, shear force and torque along the length of the beam) is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Schematic diagram of experimental set up

For a given shear force, S , applied to the end of a beam of length, L , the flap-bending moment varies linearly along the length of the beam, and is independent of the offset, y . The torque is constant along the length of the beam, but varies linearly with the offset, y .

Because the response of the beam is linear, readings at two different offsets provide sufficient information to enable the location of the shear centre to be deduced, and values of K_{44} , K_{45} and K_{55} to be determined (for symmetric beams). For each beam, measurements were taken with beams loaded in all possible orientations, and mean displacement measurements were used to calculate the stiffness terms.

Implicit in the definitions of K_{45} above is the assumption that the axial (ϵ_x), flap-shear (γ_{xy}), lag-shear (γ_{xz}), and lag-bending (κ_z) strains are all zero. In practice, this is difficult to achieve without interfering with the necessary bending displacements and imposing unknown torsion restraint forces on the section.

For symmetric lay-ups (i.e. Beams 1, 2, 4, 5 and 7) the axial, lag-shear, and lag-bending strains were all predicted to be zero under an applied flap-bending moment. These strains are not constrained and are assumed to be zero in the experimental programme. For anti-symmetric lay-ups (i.e. Beams 3, 6 and 8), a lag-shear deformation is predicted under an applied flap-bending moment. It is assumed that the presence of lag-shear bending deformation does not affect the accuracy of the displacement measurements.

It is noted that Rehfield *et al* [2] performed a four-point bending test using a “sling supported method” to measure the camber produced in a tailored box beam under bending. However, the use of such an experimental set up would make it difficult to measure the torsion force (M_{xy}) required to prevent twisting of the section.

Each beam was clamped securely at one end between two large steel blocks. Although this clamping arrangement restrains out-of-plane warping, the effects of these end restraints will die away rapidly along the length of the beam for a solid cross section.

6.1. Calculation of stiffness terms

For the end-loaded cantilever beam of length L shown in Figure 4, the bending moment is a function of applied shear load, S and coordinate, x ,

$$M_y = S(L - x) \quad (5)$$

For an end loaded cantilever beam, the flapwise deflection of a beam of width, w , thickness, t , comes from bending and shear deformations, and is given by

$$\delta_z = \frac{SL^3}{3EI} + \frac{SL}{kGtw} \quad (6)$$

where

δ_z	Flapwise tip deflection
S	Shear force
L	Length of beam
EI	Bending stiffness of beam
Gtw	Shear stiffness of beam
k	shear coefficient

The shear deflection will be small (less than 1% of the total flapwise deflection) and is thus ignored. The Euler bending deflection, $\delta_z(x)$ at coordinate x is determined from

$$\delta_z(x) = \iint \kappa_y(x) dx \quad (7)$$

Since the torque acting on the beam is constant along the length of the beam,

$$M_{yz} = Sy \quad (8)$$

and the twist, $\phi_x(x)$ is determined from

$$\phi_x(x) = \int \kappa_{yz}(x) dx \quad (9)$$

For a beam with no coupling, these calculations would be trivial. For beams with anisotropic couplings, the strains κ_{yz} and κ_y are expressed in terms of the full 6x6 matrix. For symmetric lay-ups, the K_{44} , K_{45} and K_{55} stiffness terms may be decoupled from the rest of the matrix (as described earlier), to give

$$\begin{pmatrix} M_{yz} \\ M_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{44} & K_{45} \\ K_{45} & K_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \kappa_{yz} \\ \kappa_y \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \kappa_{yz} \\ \kappa_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{44} & S_{45} \\ S_{45} & S_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} M_{yz} \\ M_y \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned}\delta_z(x) &= S \iint (S_{45}(y) + S_{55}(L-x)) dx \\ &= S \left(S_{45} \frac{yx^2}{2} + S_{55} \left(\frac{Lx^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{6} \right) \right)\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

and the end deflection is given by

$$\delta_z(L) = S \left(S_{45} \frac{yL^2}{2} + S_{55} \frac{L^3}{3} \right)\quad (13)$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_x(x) &= \int \kappa_{yz} dx \\ &= \int (S_{44}M_{yz} + S_{45}M_y) dx \\ &= S \left(S_{44}yx + S_{45} \left(Lx - \frac{x^2}{2} \right) \right)\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

and the end rotation is thus given by

$$\phi_x(L) = S \left(S_{44}yL + \frac{S_{45}L^2}{2} \right)\quad (15)$$

It is straightforward to experimentally determine the rate of change of $\phi(L)$ with respect to y . The value of S_{44} may be calculated from

$$\frac{d\phi_x(L)}{dy} = S_{44}LS\quad (16)$$

It is also straightforward to experimentally determine the value of y for which $\phi(L) = 0$. This gives the value of S_{45} as

$$S_{45} = -2S_{44} \frac{y}{L}\quad (17)$$

The end deflection for no end rotation is also easily determined, to give S_{55} from

$$\delta_x(L) = S \left(S_{45} \frac{yL^2}{2} + S_{55} \frac{L^3}{3} \right)\quad (18)$$

The flexibility terms S_{44} , S_{45} and S_{55} are now all known and (based on the location of non-zero terms predicted by classical laminate theory) the stiffness terms K_{44} , K_{45} and K_{55} for symmetric lay-ups may be calculated by inverting the 2 x 2 flexibility matrix.

7. RESULTS

A comparison of the analytical, finite element, and experimental results for each of the eight beams are presented in Figures 5-7. Because the 2x2 submatrix does not decouple from the rest of the 6x6 matrix of non-symmetric laminates, the experimental values of K_{44} , K_{45} , and K_{55} terms cannot be calculated from the measurements taken. Experimental values have not been presented for these beams on Figures 5-7.

Figure 5. Comparison of predicted and measured values for K_{44}

Figure 6. Comparison of predicted and measured values for K_{45}

Figure 7. Comparison of predicted and measured values for K_{55}

Analogy with classical laminate theory predicts that K_{45} will be zero for each of these non-symmetric specimens. It is possible to validate this prediction directly from the location of the shear centre, where the shear centre is defined as the axis through which an applied shear force will produce no twisting. The location of the shear centre relative to the centroid of the beam is shown by the variable y_0 on Figure 8.

Figure 8 Shear centre, y_0 relative to centroid of beam cross-section

If the shear centre passes through the centroid of the cross-section, then $K_{45} = 0$. Table 3 shows that the shear centre was measured to lie within a millimetre of the centroid of the beam cross section of each of the anti-symmetric beams.

Table 3 Location of shear centre relative to centroid for anti-symmetric lay-ups

Beam	Lay-up	Location of Shear Centre, y_0 (mm)				
		Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Mean
3	$[+45]_{30}[-45]_{30}$	-40.3	22.7	33.0	-15.6	-0.05
6	$[+15]_{30}[-15]_{30}$	0.5	0.5	-3.9	-0.9	-0.94
8	$[+30]_{30}[-30]_{30}$	-1.1	0.3	2.5	2.2	0.96

7.1. Comparison with of predictions with experiment

Because the assumptions of classical laminate analysis are not valid for the beam geometry studied here, there is only a loose correlation between the ABD stiffness matrix terms and the measured beam behaviour.

The values obtained from finite element analysis agree with the experimental measurements (where available) to within 10%. Within the context of the issues relating to experimental accuracy discussed below, this is felt to be close agreement and a validation of the FE method used for determining cross-sectional stiffnesses.

7.2. Discussion of Experimental Accuracy

Geometric variability: Both the thickness and width of the cross section varied slightly (~0.1mm) along the length of each beam. This corresponds to <0.5% variation in width, but approximately 1% variation in depth, which could lead to flexural inaccuracies of up to 3%.

Material properties: As noted previously, the ~8mm thick beams consisted of 60 plies each 0.125mm thick. The additional beam thickness was made up of excess resin. Taking Diamond's back-calculated values of material properties obviously introduces some uncertainty into both the analytical and finite element calculations.

Material orientation: It was assumed that plies through the thickness of the beams were laid up in the same orientation as those on the surface. The angle of surface plies was measured, and found to be within 1° of the stated orientation, except in the case of beam 8, in which the ply angle was found to differ significantly from the orientation claimed by the manufacturer (18° measured vs. 30° claimed). Finite element predictions presented by Lemanski [4] show that altering the coupling angle can have a significant effect upon K_{45} over some ranges.

Experimental procedure: The experimental procedure enabled the shear centre of a beam to be determined in a repeatable manner to within <5mm. By determining the shear centre of the beam in each possible orientation (i.e. loading both sides for both ends) and taking a mean confidence in the accuracy of the results is improved further.

It was however noted that the shear centre varied for each of the four cases – sometimes by a significant amount (e.g. spar 3). This discrepancy was found to be highly repeatable – which suggests that the experimental procedure is sound, and was measuring an inherent feature of the test specimens. This suggests that manufacturing defects and/or damage may be affecting the overall behaviour.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The fifth line of the 1-dimensional beam stiffness matrix equation describes the coupling behaviour when a slender structure is subjected to a flapwise bending moment

$$M_y = K_{15}\epsilon_x + K_{25}\gamma_{xy} + K_{35}\gamma_{xz} + K_{45}\kappa_{yz} + K_{55}\kappa_y + K_{56}\kappa_z \quad (4)$$

This is of direct relevance to beam sections that produce lifting forces, such as helicopter rotor or wind turbine blades. The distributed lifting force creates a varying flap-bending moment (M_y) along the length of the beam. K_{45} relates the value of this flexural moment to the resulting twist of the rotor blade along its length (κ_{yz}). Since twist in an aerofoil section directly affects the angle of attack, there are significant implications for lift and drag produced, as well as dynamic behaviour. It is therefore important to be able to predict (or control) how a beam cross section will twist as it produces lift by designing a blade with an appropriate value of K_{45} .

An experiment was devised that enabled the value of flexural-twist coupling to be determined. The experimental results generally supported the finite element predictions, and showed that the simplified approach of classical laminate theory is not accurate for anisotropic structures studied here. Because the sections tested are solid (rather than thin-walled) sections, the warping restraint created by clamping the root of the cantilever does not greatly affect the results. The good correlation between computational and experimental work presented here gives increased confidence in the finite element method of Hill and Weaver.

9. REFERENCES

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